

MONITORING THE DECLINE OF PLANTS AND TREES IN ANDIJAN AND VALLEY REGIONS THROUGH ARTIFICIAL ROAD IMAGES, DETERMINING THE CHANGES IN GROUNDWATER CONDITIONS WITH THE HELP OF GIS TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: The article studied the locations of plants and forests in Andijan and Valley regions by remote sensing and analyzed for 2000 and 2018 years. Based on the results of the analysis, measures for the use of groundwater in low-water areas were considered. Archival images of the Landsat satellite, cadastral map and city plan, higher-resolution satellite data of Canopus and Rapid Eye were used for research. The analysis of newly obtained multi-time thematic maps on the Andijan and Valley regions showed the diversity of the structure of its forest areas. In the south-eastern and central parts of Andijan and Valley regions, there is a significant difference in the increase and decrease in Forest and plant areas, which has a great influence on the general trend of the dynamics of landscape indicators. According to the results obtained, we can see a decrease in the class of deciduous and mixed plantations of urban forest areas in Andijan and the region under study in 18 years, the decrease is from 28108,40 to 27906,46 hectares according to data. The accuracy of the information obtained is confirmed by modern criteria of Geoinformation statistics. Compared to terrestrial research, the method of thematic mapping and evaluation of forests in regions using remote sensing methods based on landscape indicators decreases the cost of work and increases their accuracy.

Keywords: remote sensing, satellite monitoring, GIS, forest cover, satellite image, research, thematic map, geoinformation technologies, forecast, seawater water, seawater water levels.

Introduction

The relevance of research.

At present, with the help of suratlar from the satellite, it is possible to obtain qualitative and accurate information about the vegetation cover, water bodies (underground and terrestrial), irrigated areas in different areas of the territory.

Unfortunately, in Andijan and Valley regions, the use of satellite images for the purpose of studying the vegetation cover has not become popular. In this regard, it is necessary to carry out the temporary dynamics of the vegetation cover, that is, to draw the right conclusions about the decrease and increase in the number of ossicles in a given region, the use of groundwater in the regions where there is a water shortage and analyze their thematic maps. To do this, it is desirable to work with accurate results. Satellite images prove to us this and the exact result.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study is to analyze the time range of vegetation and tree growth and depletion dynamics in Andijan and valley areas with the help of remote sensing of the Earth Water Scarcity from the introduction of irrigation using groundwater.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been completed:

1. Conducting field research.
2. Selection of satellite images for the study area
3. Formation of thematic maps of vegetation cover
4. Assessment of the accuracy of thematic maps
5. Analysis of the dynamics of vegetation cover
6. Analysis of the distribution of groundwater obtained for 2021 year according to the purposes of use.
7. The goal is to select groundwater and establish the dynamics of change. (days thousand m³)

Scientific novelty of the work: The analysis of the time series of growth and depletion dynamics of plants and trees in Andijan and Valley regions with the help of remote sensing data is carried out and groundwater is analyzed. O'rtacha aniqlikdagi Landsat sun'iy yo'ldosh tasvirlari asosida o'rganilayotgan hududdagi o'simlik qoplami va daraxtlarning kamayish dinamikasi texnikasi taqdim etilgan.

Objects and subject of research: The research facilities are forested and non-forested lands in Andijan and valley areas.

Practical significance of the results obtained: The practical significance of the results obtained shows that the data on the vegetation cover and reduction of trees obtained on the basis of satellite images provide great practical assistance to forestry. it will serve as a solution to the problems of the near future with the help of previous and current information. Therefore, remote sensing methods with the use of satellite image data are of practical importance for such farms.

Basic methods: Processing of satellite images, methods for the formation of generalized classes of vegetation and trees overgrowth and depletion coating, methods for creating a Thematic Map, the distribution of areas by the depth of groundwater, the distribution of areas by the mineralization of groundwater.

PROJECT PART

Research programme: Currently, many studies are conducted on the basis of images of artificial orifices, but studies on the reduction monitoring of plants and trees in the opinion of Valley regions are very rare. In this regard, it is necessary to carry out the dynamics of the reduction of plants and trees, to distinguish areas by classification, to draw conclusions and to analyze thematic maps. We need to do the work, relying on the exact results. Satellite images prove to us this and the exact result.

Research methodology

The methodology of the work includes two stages: field and desk research.

Field research

Field research was conducted in the summer of 2018.

A detailed study and analysis of forest inventory and description of plant and tree planting plans, Cadastral data on the redistribution of Agriculture, images of medium and high-resolution satellites was carried out when choosing locations for the study of test sites.

The main criteria were: 1)for the purpose of recognition in satellite images, it is necessary to select the most represented areas of the forest land and the lands that do not have a cover of plants and trees that do not enter the forest area (figure 1-2);

2) Determine the maximum number of test sites.

Figure 1 - Test plot (TU No. 1) of the vegetation cover, covered with deciduous plantations

Figure 2 - Geographical location of the test site (TU No. 1) of the vegetation cover

The coordinates of each test site were recorded using the GARMIN eTrex GPS receiver in order to identify them on satellite images.

Figure 3 - Test plot (TU No. 2) of vegetation cover covered with mixed plantings

Figure 4 - Geographical location of the test site (TU No. 2) of the vegetation cover

Description of the software and the Landsat satellite

All work with satellite images was carried out in the software packages "ENVI 5.2", "ArcGIS 10.3" and "Topo raster".

Description of the capabilities of the ENVI 5.2 software package for processing satellite images.

Desk research

1. The procedure for monitoring vegetation cover included a number of the following stages of work carried out in the ENVI 4.8 and ArcGIS 10 software packages:
2. Selection of satellite images for the formation of thematic maps for the study area.
3. Radiometric and geometric processing of 1G level images.
4. Geo-positioning of Landsat images in the ArcGIS 10.3 PC.
5. Creation of thematic maps of 2000 and 2018 by the method of uncontrolled classification using the "IsoData" method in PC ENVI 5.2.
6. Evaluation of the accuracy of the generated thematic maps in PC ENVI 5.2.
7. Assessment of vegetation cover dynamics.

Geo-positioning of images: To analyze and display the location of satellite images in exact geographical accordance with other data, raster data needs to be linked to the existing coordinate system.

Work on linking to the geodetic coordinate system was carried out in the PC ArcGIS 10.3 in the generally accepted in Russia coordinate system Pulkovo 1942 (WGS 84).

Creation of thematic maps by the method of unmanaged classification using the "IsoData" method in PC ENVI 5.2

Two Landsat images were used in the work.

The classification was carried out in several stages.

At the first stage, it was planned to classify plants and trees, ground water, axoli living punks.

At the second stage, the climates were distinguished, in which there were plants and trees. Kolgan was removed from the class structure of the territory.

With the resulting images, we compared the object of the study and identified the regions in which there are plants and trees. (5-picture)

Figure 5 - Primary classification of the 2000 image into 25 classes

Figure 6 - Classification of satellite imagery in 2018 by the IsoData method in the PC ENVI into 20 classes

Determination of changes in the subsoil conditions of Andijan region with the help of GAT technologies.

Using "Topo raster" functions.

It was interpolated using the functions of "Topo raster", applied with respect to the point, line and polygonal data of the geologically correct raster surface. Here, the objects and its input parameters were introduced the levels of borehole and sizot waters.

Values using Layers function are shown using gradations and colors

	<p>Underground water deposits</p> <p>State</p> <p>Regional</p> <p>between areas with different depths of groundwater</p> <p>between areas with different groundwater mineralization</p>		<p>Rivers and their direction of their flow</p> <p>Large channels and their direction of their flow</p> <p>Adyrs mastered</p> <p>Adyrs undeveloped</p> <p>Mountain ranges</p>
<p>The borders</p>	<p>Other signs</p>		

Wells

The areas are distributed according to the depth of groundwater.

The area of distribution by groundwater mineralization.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Field research: As a result of field studies, 90 test sites were restored in Andijan and Valley regions of Uzbekistan. The coordinates of the location of each test site were recorded using the GARMIN eTrex GPS receiver. All data were recorded in the accounting statements (Table 2).

Table 2 – Specific features of test areas in Andijan and Valley regions of Uzbekistan.

Test section №	District	Planting composition	Average height	Average diameter
1	Izboskan district of Andijan region	Poplar	16 m	13 m
		Maple silver	29 m	18 cm
2	Balykchi district of Andijan region	Plane maple / Platan leaved maple	27 m	42 cm
		Alder gray	18 m	31 cm
		Norway spruce	34 m	20 cm

Камеральные исследования

Figure 10 - 2000 Thematic Land Cover Map

Figure 11 - Thematic land cover map 2018

The maps of the obtained cover of plants and trees reflect the distribution of classes of plants and trees in Andijan and voi regions of Uzbekistan.

Assessment of the accuracy of the thematic map of vegetation cover

In order to determine the accuracy of the classification and evaluation of the generated thematic map, post-classification processing of the received thematic vegetation map was carried out. This algorithm allows you to determine the reliability of pixels of thematic map classes by independent data using the Confusion Matrix (matrix of differences).

The average overall accuracy of the generated thematic maps of vegetation cover for 1985 and 2010 on the territory of the Mari Volga region was 71%.

In addition, to assess the accuracy of thematic maps, the Kappa coefficient was calculated, which was 0.64.

As a result, the overall accuracy and Kappa coefficient indicate a significant reliability of the generated thematic maps to independent data (field research data, map plans).

Monitoring of plants and trees in Andijan and valley areas

According to the thematic map for 2000, the area of woody and shrubby vegetation was 4733.82 thousand hectares, deciduous plantings - 28108.40 thousand hectares, shrubs – 16762.52 thousand hectares, herbaceous vegetation – 150313.32 thousand hectares

According to the thematic map for 2018, the area of woody and shrubby vegetation amounted to 5297.54 thousand hectares, deciduous plantations - 27906.46 thousand hectares, mixed – 6039.61 thousand hectares, herbaceous vegetation – 168751.40 thousand hectares.

The results obtained show a decrease or increase in the number of plants and trees in the area 18 years earlier and later.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The locations of plants and forests in Andijan and Valley regions were studied by remote sensing. A Thematic Map of the territory was created. Work was carried out on the classification of vegetation and tree cover, water bodies, residential areas and other areas. This classification work allows you to select the required fields and get information about them. On the Thematic Map, in terms of colors, areas were allocated, one of which is similar to the other. This increases the accuracy of the dimensions of the cover areas of plants and trees in the desired class. Working through GIS technologies leads to an increase in both business productivity of forestry organizations, water organizations and other organizations. Shrinking areas of plants and trees were identified in Andijan and valley areas and measures were determined to prevent shrinkage. It is advisable to use our results obtained using GIS technologies in the national project “green space”, which is being conducted on a Republican scale.

Using the results obtained by Gis technology to identify areas where water resources in Andijan region are scarce, that is, areas where water supply has become a problem, i.e. areas where plants and trees are difficult to grow, irrigation works should be introduced by mixing such areas with groundwater and trench collector waters.

The existing data on the natural and economic state of the Fergana Valley of Uzbekistan made it possible to qualitative and quantitative analysis of their impact on the economic activity of the Forest Fund and the territory under study.

Using satellite images, new thematic data were obtained on the regions of Andijan Andijan and valley of the green smell of Uzbekistan, which is necessary for monitoring the vegetation cover of the area under study.

The results of the use of remote sensing devices made it possible to obtain reliable materials necessary for subsequent evaluation and monitoring of the vegetation cover of Andijan and valley areas and to determine the change in the conditions of subsidence of groundwater.

The practical and scientific significance of the work is that, for the first time, monitoring of vegetation cover was carried out in the 18-year period (2000-2018) and medium-sized satellite images were available in the Fergana Valley region of Uzbekistan. area of forestry themed classes was determined. In addition, in the

regions under study, the method of mapping the plant cover is given by Landsat medium-resolution satellite images. The information obtained will allow you to quickly monitor changes, plan forestry activities for Forest care, as well as improve the forecasts for the development of forest landscapes and territories.

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